

Administrative Workload and Work-Related Stress Among Teachers

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Abstract

This study assessed the extent of administrative workload and work-related stress among teachers in the Luba District, focusing on the level of stress experienced in terms of administrative demands, working environment, and professional distress. A quantitative method, particularly a descriptive-correlational research design, was utilized, involving a total of 72 respondents. The needed data were gathered through survey questionnaire. The instrument was adopted from Pamunag and Mosquera (2025) and Señal and Abellana (2025). The data on the extent of teachers' administrative workload and work-related stress were analyzed using weighted means, while Pearson's r was used to test the relationship between the variables.

The study found that in Luba District teachers have a very high extent administrative workload. This has become an integral yet demanding component of their professional responsibilities. They are heavily engaged in administrative loads, which contribute to their professional growth and involvement; however, these also significantly increase the volume and complexity of teachers' workload.

Teachers experience a low level of stress in terms of their work environment. Their school provides a supportive, organized, and collegial atmosphere. However, they are highly stressed in terms of administrative demands and professional distress since they are engaged in paperwork and compliance requirements, with insufficient administrative support. Also, teachers experienced emotional and physical exhaustion, as administrative tasks affect a positive work environment. Results also show a low positive relationship between administrative workload and stress, indicating a weak but direct influence of workload on teachers' stress levels. To help teachers manage their administrative workload and stress, a Workload Balance and Stress Management Strategies for Teachers in Luba District was conceptualized.

Keywords: *Stress levels, Administrative demands, Work Environment, Professional Distress*

Introduction

Globally, teachers work beyond official hours more than other professionals (Ancho & Bongco, 2019). This is due to their increased administrative workload (Kim, 2019). As reported by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), administrative workload remains in a considerable demand for teachers. OECD reports that on average, excessive administrative work of teachers emerge as a source of work-related stress, particularly those with more than ten years of experience (OECD, 2025).

In the study by Alaiki et al. (2025), 75% of the reviewed studies identified high workloads as significant predictors of emotional exhaustion among teachers worldwide. According to Tarraya (2024), teachers' workloads are common subjects of study; however, despite the pieces of literature and the endless calls for action, this remains among the prevailing issues in the educational landscape.

The increasing workload of teachers, far exceeding that of other professions and persisting despite researches and policies (Ancho & Bongco, 2019; Pamunag & Mosquera, 2025), poses a direct threat to the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). At its core, SDG 4, ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education, relies on teachers as the primary drivers of learning outcomes, yet overburdened educators face diminished capacity to innovate, support diverse learners, and foster lifelong skills. Beyond education, excessive hours undermine SDG 8's vision of decent work and economic growth by eroding teacher well-being, productivity, and retention, while also hindering SDG 3's health targets through heightened exhaustion and SDG 10's push to reduce inequalities by widening gaps in educational access. Tackling this global issue is thus imperative to empower teachers and accelerate progress across interconnected SDGs.

To address these issues, the Department of Education (DepEd) has implemented DO No. 2, s. 2024, the goal is to simplify teachers' responsibilities, enhancing their ability to teach in class and encouraging student involvement. According to Zerna (2025), the removal of administrative tasks from teachers is beneficial, enabling them to devote more time to instructional tasks and promoting stronger collaboration among staff. The reduction in non-teaching responsibilities has allowed teachers to better concentrate on pedagogical work and engage more meaningfully with students. However, despite these policy reforms, public school teachers continue to face emerging demands and challenges following the immediate removal of administrative tasks.

During an increased administrative load, the time intended for their duties, like teaching tasks, decreased. As observed by the researcher, teachers in Luba District are required to perform excessive non-instructional duties such as maintaining school records, collecting and managing district and school-related monetary contributions, ensuring school safety, and preparing post-disaster reports for submission to DepEd portals. In addition, teachers are tasked with conducting inventories of learning materials, kitchen utensils, chairs, and tables, as well as maintaining school gardens for beautification and compliance with Healthy Barangay Award requirements.

They are also responsible for sustaining school cleanliness and beautification efforts. In case the school is understaffed, some teachers have no choice but to handle extra administrative responsibilities. Thus, the objective of the study is to investigate the extent of teachers' administrative workload and how it affects their stress in the workplace.

Literature review

This review supports the study on a broader discussion on teachers' administrative workload and their work-related stress.

Administrative Workload

In the study by Alaiki et al. (2025), 75% of the reviewed studies identified high workloads as significant predictors of emotional exhaustion among teachers worldwide. In the Malaysian context, Ani et al. (2025) reported that the teaching profession is frequently linked to stress and burnout, primarily driven by continuously evolving educational demands and increasing administrative responsibilities. These are consistent with the claim of Jerrim and Sims (2021), who examined primary and secondary teachers across five predominantly English-speaking education systems: England, Australia, Alberta (Canada), New Zealand, and the United States found that higher workloads were significantly associated with poorer teachers' wellbeing and elevated levels of workload-related stress.

Based on the data released by the OECD (2025), 17 of the 26 countries participated in a survey and found that teachers are almost the same as workers in other professions in that they "very often" work at high speed under deadlines. A high perception of work/role overload (Magtalas, 2024), particularly in teaching-related tasks and administrative duties classified as heavy to teachers (Pamunag & Mosquera, 2025). In the report of Mateo (2018), previous suicide case allegations are related to heavy workloads, and anxiety is the most prevalent mental health concern of teachers (Belarmino et al., 2025). Teachers experience a very high level of workload (Gamalo & Abellana, 2025), which made teachers take sick leave (Olivier & Venter, 2003) and leave the field (Reinke et al., 2025).

Administrative Demands

A study by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), as cited by Lague (2025), highlights teachers are frequently assigned non-teaching duties, such as paperwork related to seminars, training workshops, and tasks involving student guidance, budgeting, disaster response, and health initiatives. These responsibilities can distract teachers from their primary role of effective teaching (Orbeta et al., 2020).

Johal (2022) further posited that the most glaring effect of a teacher's high workload, like working during school holidays, is the disturbing rise in teachers leaving the profession. If these are unaddressed, consequences may continuously arise that would create a high-stress environment (Lague, 2025). When teachers are burdened with non-instructional tasks, their stress

levels increase, negatively affecting classroom performance, student engagement, and instructional effectiveness (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020; Black & Wiliam, 2009).

Shen et al. (2025) reported that school-level extra-administrative workload was significantly and positively correlated with teachers' emotional exhaustion, suggesting that administrative tasks contribute to stress. Similarly, Hussain and Malik (2025) in the district of Rahim Yar Khan found that teachers face various workload-related difficulties that negatively impact their mental and emotional health.

Working Environment

Moreover, it is noticed that teachers experience stress in their workplace while practicing their profession (Topuzi, 2018). Teachers in the Philippines experience stress and depression in their working environment (Orlanda-Ventayen & Ventayen, 2021) due to poor working environment, work overload, student misbehavior (Cabaguing, 2022), inadequate resources, and pressure to meet tight deadlines (Alson, 2009). Workplace environment remains a significant factor in teachers' stress and performance (Gonzales et., 2002) wherein physical work environment significantly influences the psychosocial work environment, which in turn significantly influences workplace stress (Becaro et al., 2023).

According to Majeed et al. (2011), an inadequate working environment is creating much stress among teachers, and teachers identified high levels in the areas of instruction management and working environment (Obrero et al., 2024). A conducive work environment plays an essential role in facilitating employee performance. Focusing on creating a positive working atmosphere and cultivating conditions that inspire productivity can significantly affect employee passion or morale (Kholis et al., 2024). In general, the teachers have moderate ability to manage stress, which is indicative of a fairly good level of adaptability in coping with demands and responsibilities at the workplace (Gudelos et al., 2025).

Professional Distress

In the educational system, stress and burnout are always described as a main public health challenge. As the teaching profession has undergone different changes, with professional demands and responsibilities increasing, burnout and occupational stress have increased too. As a result, all of these contribute to professional distress among teachers ("What's Causing Teacher Burnout?," 2024). Kilburg et al. (1988) also explained that distressed professionals may experience boredom, fatigue, or loss of interest in work. In addition, psychological distress is generally referred to as depression, anxiety, stress, and mental health-related problems (Dyrbye et al., 2010). The level of psychological distress among teachers is twice that expected in the general population (Punch & Tuettemann, 1990). High prevalence of psychological distress (55.6 %), anxiety (17.0%), and depression (28.4 %) among Filipino university teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic (Mordeno et al., 2023).

Conceptual Framework

The study is anchored on the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Theory, the Job Demand-Control (JDC) Model by Karasek (1979), and Role Theory by Biddle (1986). Together, these explain how teachers' administrative workload affects their stress levels. The JD-R theory shows that every job has specific demands and resources. Job demands require ongoing physical or mental effort and can lead to psychological strain. In this study, tasks like maintaining school records, completing school reports, and fulfilling non-instructional responsibilities are considered job demands that add stress to teachers. On the other hand, job resources with a lesser administrative workload and a supportive working environment can help reduce the negative effects of these demands. This theory supports the idea that lowering administrative workload decreases job demands, which then reduces teachers' stress levels.

Supporting the JD-R theory, the Job Demand-Control (JDC) Model indicates that high job demands impact teachers' stress. In this study, the number of administrative workloads show high job demands, while limited control over non-teaching tasks signifies low job control. This situation leads to more stress for teachers. Additionally, role theory explains that stress increases when people face role overload or role conflict due to too many responsibilities. Teachers who must handle both instructional and non-instructional duties are more likely to experience professional distress and emotional exhaustion.

Together, these theories provide the foundation for this study. As illustrated in Figure 1, the researcher adopted the independent variable–dependent variable (IV–DV) model. The independent variable consists of teachers' administrative workload that includes tasks like paperwork, report preparation, compliance requirements, and other non-instructional duties. The dependent variable measured the level of stress of teachers within the three dimensions: administrative demands, working environment, and professional distress. The study's output develops proposed stress management activities for teachers.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

Research Question

This study aimed to describe the administrative workload and the stress level among teachers of Luba District during the year 2025-2026. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the assigned administrative loads of teachers?
2. What is the level of work-related stress of teachers along;
 - a. Administrative demands,
 - b. Working environment, and
 - c. Professional distress?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of teachers' administrative workload and their level of stress?
4. What programs or activities can be proposed to support teachers in coping with administrative workload?

Research Methodology

This section presents and describes the methodology used in the study, which included the research design, population sampling, locale of the study, data-gathering instruments and procedure, ethical considerations, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative method, particularly the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive–correlational research design is used to determine the extent of teachers' administrative workload and the level of stress experienced by teachers. Further, the correlational aspect enabled an investigation of the relationship between the extent of administrative tasks and teachers' stress levels without manipulating any variables. This design sought to identify the link between the administrative workload and stress of teachers in terms of administrative demands, working environment, and professional distress without attempting to manipulate any of them (Copeland, 2022). A descriptive-correlational approach was used to describe relationships between groups in a population that was not subjected to any manipulation (Cantrell, 2011).

Population and Locale

The respondents of the study were all the permanent teachers in both complete

elementary and primary schools in Luba District during the School Year 2025-2026. Total enumeration was employed, comprising 72 teachers.

The locale of the study is in Luba, which is a mountainous place found in the southern part of Abra with 8 Barangays. The geographical characteristics of each barangay, including the distance from the school, affect the accessibility of work.

Data Gathering Instrument

A questionnaire was used as the main tool in gathering data. This consisted of two parts. The first part is a 20-item questionnaire that assessed the extent of teachers' administrative workload, adopted from Pamunag and Mosquera (2025). The second part measured the level of stress of teachers along administrative demands, working environment, and professional distress adopted from the study of Señal and Abellana (2025).

A 4-point Likert scale was used to measure the extent of administrative Workload of teachers in Luba District. This was further analyzed using the scale and descriptive equivalent.

Statistical Limit	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating	Descriptive	Equivalent
3.25-4.00	4	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
2.50-3.24	3	Agree	High Extent	
1.75-2.49	2	Disagree	Low Extent	
1.0-1.74	1	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Extent	

Moreover, A 5-point Likert scale was used to measure the level of stress of teachers in Luba District in terms of Administrative Demands, Working Environment, and Professional Distress. This was also analyzed using the scale and descriptive equivalent.

Statistical Limit	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating	Descriptive	Equivalent
4.21-5.00	5	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41-4.20	4	Agree	High	
2.61-3.40	3	Neutral	Moderate	

1.81-2.60	2	Disagree	Low
1.00-1.80	1	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Data Gathering Procedures

Formal requests for permission to gather data were submitted to the Schools Division Office of Abra and to the school principals of the participating public elementary schools in Luba District. Upon approval, a letter was attached to the survey questionnaires to inform the teacher-respondents about the objectives of the study, the procedures involved, and their rights as respondents.

Sufficient time was provided for the participants to answer the instrument at their convenience, ensuring accuracy and thoughtful responses. The researcher coordinated with the administrative officer in each school for the smooth distribution and retrieval of the questionnaires.

The questionnaires were collected, checked for completeness, and systematically tallied. The data were then encoded and prepared for statistical analysis in accordance with the research design. Throughout the entire process, voluntary participation, anonymity, and confidentiality of responses were strictly upheld to protect the welfare and privacy of the participants.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To substantiate the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data, the following statistical tasks are utilized.

1. Weighted mean was used to describe the extent of teachers' administrative workload and their level of stress.
2. Pearson (r) was used to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the extent of teachers' administrative load and level of stress.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents during the conduct of the study. Policies and protocols of the Department of Education were strictly observed in the acquisition of necessary information from the respondents. Consent from the Schools Division Superintendent, as well as from the school heads and teachers, is also requested. The researcher ensured that the results of the study contributed to the wellness of teachers. The researcher observed proper acknowledgment of all sources, ensuring compliance with academic integrity through respectful citations and references.

Results

This section presents the interpretation and analysis of the data gathered on the extent of administrative workload and the level of stress of teachers in Luba District.

Problem 1. What is the extent of administrative Loads of the teachers of Luba District?

Table 1 presents the extent of the administrative workload of teachers of Luba District.

The table reveals that the elementary teachers of Luba District have a “very high” extent of administrative workload, as supported by the computed area mean of 3.50. This means that the teachers are performing non-instructional tasks like participation in government programs, Learning Resource (LR) coordinators, and Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) coordinators, which are not the primary focus in delivering quality instruction. It can also be gleaned from the table that the indicators “conducting meetings with parents or guardians to discuss students’ progress, address concerns and foster a collaborative relationship between home and school” garnered the highest mean of 3.76 described as very high extent. This means that teachers recognize their role in initiating a collaboration mechanism with their pupils’ parents. It is also good to highlight that the respondents have a very high extent of collaboration with external stakeholders for programs and projects and with non-government organizations focused on education, social service, or community development. It can also be deduced from the table that the respondents have a “very high” extent of being assigned as leads, providing an extent of analyzing student data; tracking learners’ progress; providing insights to inform instructional planning and decision-making; and collaborating with local educational agencies, such as the district and division teams, to contribute to educational policies and others.

The lowest computed mean falls on the item assigned to mentors to support and guide new or less experienced teachers, providing instructional assistance, advice, and professional development opportunities, which is also interpreted as “very high.” This shows that teachers recognized the idea of shared and distributed leadership.

Table 1

Level of Stress of Teachers in Terms of Administrative Workload

Administrative Workload	Mean	DE
1. Assigned to serve as coordinators within their grade level, responsible for facilitating collaboration, curriculum alignment, and communication among colleagues.	3.65	VHE
2. Assigned as non-academic coordinator. (Sports, gulayan etc.).	3.49	VHE
3. Conducts meetings with parents or guardians to discuss student progress, address concerns, and foster a collaborative relationship between home and school.	3.76	VHE
4. Assigned as mentors to support and guide new or less experienced teachers, providing instructional assistance, advice, and professional development opportunities.	3.27	VHE
5. Collaborates with educators from other schools to share resources, exchange best practices.	3.54	VHE

6. Collaborates with external stakeholders for programs and projects	3.70	VHE
7. Assigned as leads, providing guidance, support, and professional development opportunities for other teachers in particular subject area.	3.34	VHE
8. Assigned to facilitate Learning Action Cell meetings, guiding colleagues in collaborative discussions to improve instructional practices and student learning outcomes.	3.38	VHE
9. Organizes and facilitates workshops or informational sessions for parents.	3.39	VHE
10. Participates in professional learning networks or organizations, attending conferences and workshops.	3.68	VHE
11. Participates to local government activities.	3.55	VHE
12. Assigned to analyze student data, track progress, and provide insights to inform instructional planning and decision-making.	3.74	VHE
13. Assigned to serve on the school improvement committee, actively participating in discussions and decision-making processes related to school improvement initiatives.	3.58	VHE
14. Assigned as liaisons between the school and the PTA, facilitating communication, coordinating events, and fostering parent involvement.	3.49	VHE
15. Participates in training sessions or is invited as a guest speaker to specialized fields of expertise, and real-life experiences beyond the classroom.	3.36	VHE
16. Assigned as advisors or sponsors for clubs, extracurricular activities, or student organizations, overseeing and supporting student involvement in these activities.	3.46	VHE
17. Assigned to oversee the administration and coordination of assessments, including organizing testing schedules, training staff, and ensuring assessment protocols are followed.	3.42	VHE
18. Engages with the local community by organizing or participating in events, volunteering, or establishing partnerships with community organizations.	3.45	VHE
19. Collaborates with non-government organizations focused on education, social services, or community development.	3.28	VHE
20. Collaborate with local educational agencies, such as the district, division teams, to contribute to educational policies, and others.	3.38	VHE
Area Mean	3.50	VHE

Legend:

Statistical Limits Descriptive Equivalent

3.25-4.00 *Very High Extent (VHE)*

2.50-3.24 *High Extent (HE)*

1.75-2.49 *Low Extent (LE)*

1.0-1.74 *Very Low Extent (VLE)*

Problem 2. What is the level of stress of teachers along a) administrative demands, b) working environment and c) professional distress?

Table 2 presents the level of stress of teachers in terms of Administrative Demands.

It can be deduced from the table that elementary teachers have a “High” Level of stress, as supported by the computed area mean of 3.78. This shows that the respondents are experiencing psychological strains arising not from their core instructional roles, but from the cumulative burden of paperwork, compliance reporting, and documentation activity. The volume and complexity of non-instructional tasks is draining their physical and emotional resources. Further, the result implies that the teachers are facing role conflict and role overload.

Among all the indicators, reducing administrative demands worked significantly to decrease my stress levels at work garnered the highest computed mean of 4.24, interpreted as very high. This reveals that the administrative workload is the primary and pervasive source of stress of teachers.

In relation, the respondents perceive a high level of stress in terms of the validity of administrative requirements and managing paperwork and documentation. This means that the respondents are generally stressed and aware of frequent policy shifts and inconsistent echoes. In the course of complying with these varying directives, the forms to be accomplished divert them from teaching and working exhaustion.

Furthermore, the indicator I often feel unsupported by the administration in meeting administrative demands received the lowest computed mean, indicating moderate support. This means that teachers occasionally encounter difficulties in fulfilling administrative requirements due to the way their school leaders support them.

As found by Kerr, n.d., administrative support is critical in maintaining teachers' stress levels. When support is perceived as inadequate, teachers may feel isolated, undervalued, or overwhelmed, which contributes to stress. Meanwhile, the study of Taggart (2021) revealed that a higher ratio of faculty to some types of non-instructional workers is associated with increased faculty member stress.

Legend:

Statistical Limit Descriptive Equivalent

4.21-5.00	<i>Very High (VH)</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>High (H)</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Moderate (M)</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Low (L)</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Very Low (VL)</i>

Table 2

Level of stress of teachers in terms of Administrative Demands

Administrative Demands	Mean	DE
1. The variability in administrative requirements increases my stress	4.00	H
2. I struggle to balance administrative responsibilities with classroom instruction.	3.82	H
3. I often feel unsupported by my administration in meeting administrative demands.	3.10	M
4. Managing paperwork and documentation adds to my feeling of professional burnout.	3.92	H
5. I often feel anxious about meeting deadlines for administrative tasks.	3.83	H
6. The administrative demands placed on me contribute significantly to my overall stress.	3.66	H
7. I find that the administrative tasks distract me from my primary role as an educator.	3.83	H
8. The time spent on administrative tasks prevents me from engaging in self-care practices.	3.69	H
9. I worry that my inability to complete administrative tasks will affect my evaluations or job security.	3.76	H
10. Reducing administrative demands would significantly decrease my stress levels at work.	4.24	VH
Area Man	3.78	H

Table 3 presents the level of stress of teachers in terms of Working Environment.

It can be deduced from the table that the teachers of Luba District have a “very low” level of stress in terms of working environment. This shows that the respondents have a conducive working environment, which is needed to perform work productively. Teachers generally experience a healthy and supportive working environment.

The findings support the study of Punch and Tuetteman (1996), revealing that supportive relationships within the work environment and recognition can reduce or counteract the stress. On the contrary, Richards et al. (2018) concluded that teachers experience high levels of stress and burnout in their working environment.

Taking it singly, the respondents have a “very low” level of stress in terms of the role of peer support in promoting adherence to school policies”. This means that the respondents

recognize the beauty of having a good relationship with their peers. Consequently, the respondents have a very low level of stress in terms of the Staff members who demonstrate a commitment to upholding school policies. They can observe that all of the personnel are doing their best in their assigned tasks.

Table 3

Level of stress of teachers in terms of Working Environment

Working Environment	Mean	DE
1. I believe that policy compliance is valued and recognized within the school community.	1.61	VL
2. Feedback on policy compliance is constructive and helpful	1.63	VL
3. I receive guidance on how to adhere to school policies effectively.	1.72	VL
4. Peer support plays a role in promoting adherence to school policies.	1.51	VL
5. Staff members demonstrate a commitment to upholding school policies.	1.56	VL
6. I feel encouraged to follow school policies by the school administration.	1.68	VL
7. There are resources available to help me comply with school policies.	1.76	VL
8. There is adequate support provided to ensure compliance with school policies.	1.82	L
9. Training sessions are conducted to enhance understanding of school policies.	1.59	VL
10. The consequences of non-compliance with policies are clearly communicated.	1.79	VL
	Area Mean	1.67 VL

Legend:

<i>Statistical Limits</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>Very High (VH)</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>High (H)</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Moderate (M)</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Low (L)</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Very Low (VL)</i>

The respondents further perceived that they have a “low” level of stress in terms of the adequacy of support provided to ensure compliance with the school policies, and very low in clear dissemination of the consequences of non-compliance with policies. This shows that school provides a generally organized and well-guided working environment. The teachers do not feel heavily pressured or confused because they are sufficiently supported in understanding and following school policies. Thus, when teachers know that assistance is available, they are more

likely to feel confident in carrying out policy requirements. Moreover, the result implies that the respondents recognize the structured system where policies are being implemented. They can see rules that are easy to understand, especially when these are disseminated or oriented to teachers.

The findings contradict the claim of Kavenuke and Kinyota (2022) that support from administrators and mechanisms for collegiality are needed, suggesting potential inadequacies in support for policy compliance and dissemination of consequences. Also, Gobena (2020) and Berryhill et al. (2009) concluded that teachers experience high levels of stress due to school administrative policies and support.

Table 4 presents the level of stress of teachers in terms of Professional Distress

Table 4

Level of stress of teachers in terms of Professional Distress

Professional Distress	Mean	DE
1. I have too many responsibilities to complete in the time allotted.	3.74	H
2. I feel emotionally drained after a day of teaching.	3.89	H
3. I find it difficult to cope with the demands of my job.	3.44	H
4. I have often been bothered that I have trouble concentrating on things like school work, reading, or watching TV.	3.30	M
5. I feel emotionally drained after a day of teaching.	3.63	H
6. I feel that inadequate resources make my job more difficult.	3.72	H
7. The flexibility of my schedule allows me to attend to personal commitments effectively.	3.77	H
8. I experience physical symptoms (e.g., headaches, fatigue) due to work stress.	3.78	H
9. My current role as a teacher allows for adequate time for relaxation activities outside of work.	3.48	H
10. I worry about job security or performance evaluations	3.57	H
Area Mean	3.63	H

Legend:

<i>Statistical Limits</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>Very High (VH)</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>High (H)</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Moderate (M)</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Low (L)</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Very Low (VL)</i>

The table unveils that the teachers of Luba district have a “high” level of professional distress. This reveals that the respondents are experiencing substantial pressure in their professional roles, suggesting that the demands of teaching may be exceeding the support and resources available to them. This also means that work conditions are likely to affect their emotional, physical, and mental well-being because of the challenging and demanding working environment. Hence, the pressure on the work of respondents is outweighing the support, time and resources available needed in assuming their roles comfortably.

Looking close to the table, it can be noticed that the teachers feel emotionally drained after a day of teaching. This is no longer surprising due to the volume of tasks assigned to them. Consequently, the respondents have a high level of stress since there are too many responsibilities to complete in the allotted time, and experience physical symptoms like headaches and fatigue due to work stress. This indicates that teachers handle more responsibilities beyond what is required and expected of them.

Furthermore, teachers are often bothered and troubled by concentrating on things like schoolwork, reading, or watching TV. This reflects a moderate level of professional distress in teachers. As stated in the framework of the Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) model, these distractions may contribute to the cumulative effect of job demands that require sustained cognitive and emotional effort. Despite the different intensifying workloads assigned to them, teachers demonstrate flexibility by using their abilities and focusing on their professional responsibilities. Additionally, they are still able to allocate time for personal activities such as reading and watching television, suggesting that the distress experienced is manageable and moderated by effective coping mechanisms and personal resources. As cited by Tarraya (2023), although heavy workloads lead to some negative outcomes like high emotional stress and feelings of tiredness, which hamper the teachers' capability to teach. In the study of Gul et al. (2021) that increase in teachers' workload decreases teachers' time management skills in their professional roles and recreation.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of teachers' administrative workload and their level of stress?

Table 5 presents the analysis on the significant relationship between the extent of teachers' administrative workload and their level of stress.

Table 5

Correlation of the Administrative Workload and the Level of Stress of teachers of Luba District.

Correlates	p-value	Decision
Extent of Workload and Level of Stress of Teachers	0.32	Low Positive Significant Relationship

*0.05 level of Significance

The table reveals that there is a low positive significant relationship between the extent of workload and level of stress of teachers, as supported by the computed p-value of 0.32. This means that as the administrative workload increases, stress also tends to increase, but only to a small extent. The workload has a direct but weak relationship on teachers' stress levels. Thus, while workload contributes to stress, it is not the primary or sole factor affecting how stressed teachers feel. This further means that teachers' stress is not only determined by workload, but rather a combination of other factors in the working environment. This is attributed to the experiences of teachers in the field. It has been included in their routine activities, causing their workload to affect their level of stress to a low positive extent. Teachers may still experience manageable stress levels despite increased workload, possibly due to effective coping strategies, professional experience, or supportive school environments. Conversely, some teachers may experience high stress even with lighter workloads due to other pressures such as student behavior, administrative expectations, or lack of resources. This is corroborated by Maguate (2024), who persist other factors, like large class sizes, student behavior, financial concerns, and lack of administrative support, cause higher stress for teachers.

The result supports the study of Shen et al. (2025), reporting that administrative workload was significantly and positively correlated with teachers' emotional exhaustion, suggesting that administrative tasks contribute to stress. Similarly, Hussain and Malik (2025) found that teachers face various workload-related difficulties that negatively impact their mental and emotional health. On the other hand, the findings contradict Cadimas and Canape (2025) and Jaafar et al. (2020), who concluded that general workload does not significantly affect teachers' stress levels.

Problem 4. What programs or activities can be proposed to support teachers in coping with administrative workload?

LEARNING PROGRAM PROPOSAL

General Objectives

This Learning Program aims to provide teachers with concrete strategies for coping to them and their stress levels. Topics are also specially designed to help them understand their workload while managing stress.

DISTRICT LEARNING PROGRAM PROPOSAL

Division/Section/District/School: DIVISION OF ABRA/LUBA DISTRICT

Date: May 21,2026 Tracking /Control # (to be assigned by the HRDS):

I. TITLE	Workload Balance and Stress Management Strategies for Teachers in Luba District
II. PROPONENT	RODELYN D. CABANDAY
III. DATE/S	May 21, 2026
IV. VENUE	Lul-luno Elementary School
V. PARTICIPANTS	Total no. of participants: 72 teachers, 6 school heads and 1 non-teaching
VI. RATIONALE	<p>The volume of administrative workload of teachers of Luba District found out that it contributes to their stress. In the study conducted, it is also reflected that teachers perform a variety of work affecting their work. Similarly, in the study of Kim (2019), even if teachers are highly motivated, excessive paperwork can undermine and affect the quality of teaching and later learning outcomes.</p> <p>Despite the implementation of the policies in DepEd Order no. 2 s. 2024: the removal of administrative tasks of teachers and DepEd Order no. 5 s. 2024 mandating the no. of hours of actual classroom teaching and the compensation of overtime spent in teaching duties, challenges are still present. These include gaps in policy implementation and lack of clear dissemination of works and are seen as one of the reasons why teachers are still overwhelmed with their work.</p>

	<p>In response to this concern, this training is designed to support teachers in balancing the increasing administrative workload (paperwork, reports, compliance tasks) while reducing stress levels related to administrative demands, working environment, and professional distress.</p>
VII. OBJECTIVES	<p>By the end of the training, participants should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify major sources of administrative workload stress • Apply time-management and task-prioritization strategies • Improve efficiency in accomplishing reports and compliance requirements • Develop coping strategies for professional distress • Foster a more supportive and collaborative working environment
VIII. TARGET COMPETENCY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-Management • Work Balance • Stress management • Service Orientation
IX. ALIGNMENT TO THE OPCRF (SDO/School)	<p>KRA 1 – Instructional Leadership</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing workload and stress improves teaching effectiveness • Teachers can better focus on instruction and learner outcomes • It strengthens classroom performance through improved teacher capacity and well-being <p>KRA 3 – Human Resource Management and Professional Development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting teacher well-being and welfare • Addressing teacher workload and stress management <p>KRA 4 – School Operations and Resource</p>

	Management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient workload distribution improves school operations • Proper management of tasks and compliance requirements supports organizational efficiency 		
X. ALIGNMENT TO THE PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS	Domain 7: Personal Growth and Professional Development Strands: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strand 7.1 (Philosophy of Teaching): Implicitly encourages a manageable, learner-centered teaching philosophy that reduces unnecessary work-related stress. 2. Strand 7.3 (Professional Links and Reflection): Encourages reflection on one's practice, which includes managing personal and professional well-being. 4. School policies and procedures 		
XI. MATRIX OF ACTIVITIES and LIST OF RESOURCE PERSONS <i>***pls. include pre and post tests as appropriate***</i>	Day and Time	Topic/Activity	Resource Person/In-Charge
	May 21, 2026		
	7:00 AM - 7:30 AM	Attendance / Registration	Teachers, Pupils and Parents
	7:30 AM - 7:35 AM	Prayer	Darsy G. Tabag, TIII
	7:35 AM - 7:40 AM	National Anthem	Mhebe D. Collo, TVI
	7:40 AM - 7:50 AM	Welcome Message	Lester G. Viernes, P1
	7:50 AM - 8:40 AM	Objectives and Rationale	Rodelyn D. Cabanday, T3
	8:40 AM - 10:00 AM	Understanding Administrative Workload	Invited Speaker

		(DepEd Order No. 2 s. 2024 and DepEd Order No.5 s. 2024)		
	10:00AM – 10:20 AM	SNACK		
	10:20 AM - 11:40 AM	Time Management and Task Prioritization	Invited Speaker	
	11:40 AM- 1:30 PM	LUNCH BREAK		
	1:30 AM- 2:40 PM	Stress Management and Professional Well-being	Invited Speaker	
	2:40 PM – 3:50 PM	Enhancing Working Management	Invited Speaker	
	3:50 PM – 4:50 PM	Giving of Certificates and Pictorials		
	4:50- 5:00	Closing Prayer		
XII. METHODOLOGY	Face to face in an open area Lecture Discussion Workshop			
XIII. MANAGEMENT TEAM/Learning Facilitators/ QAME in-charge <i>***for SDO-based LPs, ALWAYS</i> <i>include 1 slot each for HRD and SMME personnel***</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Program Coordinator: Rodelyn D. Cabanday •Facilitators: Rodelyn D. Cabanday, Invited Speakers •Documenters: Derna G. Gayyed, Administrative Officer •Technical Support: Jovelyn S. Gayyed, Darsy G. Tabag 			
BUDGETARY REQUIREMENTS	Particulars	Unit	Price/unit	Total
Grand Total:				

Certified as to the availability of fund:	
Prepared by:	RODELYN D. CABANDAY Date signed: _____
Checked and Reviewed:	EDEN T. ADRIATICO SEPS-HRD/Division GAD Coordinator Date: _____
Recommending Approval:	<i>For school-based:</i> LESTER G. VIERNES Principal-I Date: _____
Approved:	AMADOR D. GARCIA SR., PhD, CESO V Schools Division Superintendent Date: _____

Discussion

The result of the study provides a deeper understanding on the extent of administrative workload of teachers and the level of their work-related stress such as the administrative demands, working environment and professional distress in Luba District. Based on the data gathered, the respondents shows that they have a high extent of administrative workload such as conducting meetings with the parents/guardians, organizing collaborative activities and collaborating with external stakeholders for programs and projects and with non-government organizations focused on education, social service, or community development. These have become a continuous and frequently time-consuming aspect of the teachers of Luba district in their responsibilities in their respective schools.

Likewise, these administrative workloads of teachers contributed to their stress. Administrative demands found out to cause a high level of stress to teachers. They experience psychological strains arising not from their core instructional roles, but from cumulative burden of paperwork, compliance reporting, and documentation activity.

Consequently, teachers have a very low level of stress in terms of their working environment. They have a conducive working environment that motivates the needed to perform their work productively. School policies are not viewed as a major source of stress. Teacher also

do not feel heavily pressured because they are sufficiently supported in understanding and following school policies.

Furthermore, teachers have a high level of professional distress. They are experiencing substantial pressure in their professional roles. The demands of teaching may exceed the support and resources available to them. Hence, their work conditions affect their emotional, physical, and mental well-being because of the challenging and demanding working environment. The respondents handle more responsibilities beyond what is required and expected of them.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The administrative workload of elementary teachers of Luba District has become an integral yet demanding component of their professional responsibilities. Beyond their primary instructional roles, teachers are heavily engaged in tasks such as parent coordination, report preparation, mentoring, participation in professional development, and collaboration with various stakeholders. While these responsibilities contribute positively to professional growth and school-community partnerships, they also significantly increase the volume and complexity of teachers' workload.

Teachers experience a high level of stress due to administrative demands, largely driven by paperwork, compliance requirements, and insufficient perceived administrative support. While efforts are being made by school leaders to mitigate these demands, they may not be fully addressing teachers' needs for assistance and workload balance.

Conversely, in terms of working environment, schools in Luba District provide a supportive, organized, and collegial atmosphere. Positive peer relationships and clear policy structures help buffer the negative effects of workload, demonstrating the importance of a healthy organizational climate in reducing stress.

However, despite this supportive environment, teachers still report a high level of professional distress, characterized by emotional exhaustion, physical fatigue, and pressure from excessive responsibilities. The intensity and volume of tasks outweigh the protective effects of a positive work environment, ultimately affecting teachers' well-being.

There is a low positive relationship between the administrative workload and the stress of the teachers. The workload has a direct but weak influence on teachers' stress levels. Thus, while workload contributes to stress, it is not the primary or sole factor affecting how stressed teachers feel. School Heads are recommended to review the administrative workload and school leaders like Principals and Master Teachers can strengthen support mechanisms through regular LAC sessions focused on administrative efficiency, such as template-based reporting tools and digital platforms (e.g., Google Workspace or DepEd Commons) to streamline paperwork.

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